
**Best Practices at B. V's Matoshri Bayabai Shripatrao Kadam
Mahavidyalaya, Kadegaon, Dist. Sangli**

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Abstract:

This paper is mainly focused on various best practices to be followed by our library. It discusses importance of introducing best practices in academic library to improve its process and activities, optimize resource utilization and deliver high quality, services to library users. The paper is mainly focused on various best practices to be followed in Academic Libraries. The explosion of information and the popularity of the internet, libraries have faced new challenges to look for new ways to meet the user's new demands and expectations. The need to bring information to various users has encouraged the creation of many innovative services linking new technology with traditional library services. This article explores new innovative library services to increase the use of library and its services & full fill patrons requirements related to information.

Keywords: Library Services, Best Practices, Innovation

Introduction:

Bharati Vidyapeeth's Matoshri Bayabai Shripatrao Kadam Kanya Mahavidyalaya, Kadegaon, the college that stands for excellence and continuously sets the highest standards though situated in remote rural area. Hon. Dr. Patangrao Kadam keeping in mind the motto of the parent institute has started the college for socially and economically backward girl students. This is the only multi-faculty college in rural area which boasts good infrastructure and other facilities. The institute is located with a beautiful, scenic background in 22.5 acres of land and the boundaries are demarcated by the compound wall. The institution has spacious campus for the purpose of organizing academic, sports, and administrative activities.

The only multi-faculty college in rural area for girls under Shivaji University, Kolhapur. The only college in rural area with

good infrastructure & other facilities. No one is deprived of higher education. Adopts students from economically weaker sections of the society. Concessions in tuition fees, hostel fees, mess fees, examination fees, bus passes etc. Staff contributes to these concessions through Samadhan fund. Well developed play ground, Indoor and Outdoor Sports Facilities. Open air stage for cultural activities. Hostel with concession / subsidized rates. Pure & adequate water supply. Short term career oriented courses for empowerment. Extension activities for personality development. Computer & Internet facility. Guidance for competitive exams. Scholarships and freeships as per the rules of State and Central Government fee structure. Teachers with academic excellence.

Vision:

- To provide value-added services to the differently abled, female students, and

researchers inside and outside the institute.

- To create the best citizens for nation-building.

Objectives:

1. To promote reading habits.
2. To provide a proper knowledge resource to a proper user.
3. To provide qualitative services to users.
4. To save the time of the user or reader.
5. To arrange library activities for library users for Development users satisfaction is ultimate aim of Library.

Our Library:

Library is spacious and well furnished with total built-up area of 180.00 Sq.m including textbook section, reference section, periodical section, Faculty and staff reading room, Student reading room with seating capacity of 50 users. The number of books are 30328 with 18918 titles, 341 bound volumes, 2380 donated books, 70 CDs, 23 journal periodical, 9 daily newspapers. Internet facility -5 computers are available for students in library. The library provides open access to users in reference section, periodical section and also textbook section.

The library is fully computerized and atomized by using e-granthalaya software. OPAC is also provided for searching the books. Access to e- Books and e-journals is made from INFLIBNET and NDLI. The barcode system is used for effective and speedy transaction of books. User Tracker system is used in library.

- The library is fully automated. With the help of NIC's e-Granthalaya, Integrated Library Management System (ILMS).
- A Digital Agenda for Library Automation and Networking is an Integrated Library Management

Software from National Informatics Centre, (NIC), Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, Government of India.

- The software provides built-in LAN base OPAC. One computer made available for OPAC facility.
- All books are entire in the Software with Barcode. It is enabled for user friendly circulation.
- The library is using the User Tracking System Software.
- The library is using the Scanner for the easy to circulation for the users.
- The library is providing the smart library card for the easy to circulation, through the e-Granthalaya.

Facilities:

- Audio visual CD facility
- Book bank facility
- Books for comp. exam
- Carrier development related information and newspaper clipping Display and notification.
- Library user orientation or information literacy to new unrolled
- Internet facility
- New arrival Display.
- Open access facility.
- Previous question papers
- Reading room facility
- Reprography facility.
- Inter library loan
- Newspaper clipping
- Free e-resources for Differently abled students
- Free online e-resources
- Open access facility.
- Syllabus
- CCTV
- Vachan Prerna din & Book Exhibition

Student Orientation:

Librarian conducts regularly Information Literacy Programme for entire learner community among Arts, Commerce and science stream. Through this programme, it is attempted to awareness among students about print as well as e-based resources and valuable services which are provided by central library. Besides this, practical experience is provided about various electronic based resources as well as open educational resources with hand on practice on computer as well as with smart phone.

MOU of SUCLA (SUCLA Online Union Catalogue):

MoU is signed with Shivaji University College Librarian Association (SUCLA) under which online Library OPAC is accessible 24x7 by users. It is a resource sharing initiative by the university. Users can remotely access database of the university and affiliated colleges. Users from the university and other colleges are able to access our Library resources. They can easily search and locate the required book in any member libraries.

Book Bank Facility:

Our Institute Library provides Book Bank facility to the students. Main aim of Book Bank is to encourage the meritorious students by providing informational and educational assistance from the institute itself. In an academic institute, every user may not be economically rich. User with sound finance can buy the books from their own but user with poor economic background can't afford to buy their required information sources. So, for their study materials, they have to totally rely on the library. But 'Limited collection of libraries' reason which prevents issuing a particular document to a few students at a time. Practicing book bank services in library can help to overcome such a situation to some extent. Book Banks are developed for the

upliftment of the economically backward, differently abled, backward class students and to reduce the rate of failure among them.

Library Card /Barrow Card Printing:

Smart Card Integration - Smart Card is a kind of Identity Card, Smart card can be used in eG3 for ISSUE of the books. For using smart card swap the card in card reader

Library User Tracker System Software:

Library user's attendance paperless in-out record. The library keeps a record of every member coming and going to the library, which member came when. How much time did he spend in the library. The library has many visitors, every institute issues an ID card to each student, and the ID card is encrypted. With the help of barcodes, we can calculate library members. One in front of the main lobby of the library Commands to compute with a computer as well as each other that occurs when a binary code is connected to the same computer. By showing your ID card to a student or staff member, you will be admitted to the library. In case of withdrawal as well as withdrawal, the same should be recorded in the Library Accounts Register. Report on how long the member sat in the library or returned to the library. By commanding the calculation, you will know immediately the librarian will take a printout of the report and keep it in the file or stored in PDF, Excel any soft copy format or e-mail Reports.

N-LIST:

The Project entitled "National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (NLIST)", is being jointly executed by the e-ShodhSindhu Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDESTAICTE Consortium, IIT Delhi. Our library are a regular subscriber of N-List . The N-LIST project provides access to e-resources to students, researchers and faculty from colleges

and other beneficiary institutions through server(s) installed at the INFLIBNET Centre. The users from colleges can now access e-resources and download articles required by them directly from the publisher's website once they are duly authenticated as authorized users through servers deployed at the INFLIBNET Centre.

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Pest Controlling of Library:

In our institute for preservation & conservation of library Books we undertake a activity by professional pest controller to save a books & other Library material from Insects.

Insects and vermin are naturally attracted to paper because paper is made of cellulose, starch and protein, materials that provide sources of nourishment. The most common pests are roaches, silverfish, and various types of beetles. Book lice feed on mold spores found on paper and cardboard, and although they do not cause visible damage, their decomposition and excretions can stain paper and may also nourish other pests, continuing the cycle of damage freezing collection items can mitigate pests. However, some materials should not be frozen, such as books made with leather, because the cold temperatures may cause the fat to rise to the surface of the leather resulting in a white or yellow area called a bloom. The use of insecticides directly on collection materials is not generally recommended. However, if the

infestation is severe, and fumigation is the best option, the affected items should be separated from the rest of the collection for treatment.

- Action taken to preserve digital objects whether created from analog collection or born digital objects.
- Conservation of original analog objects.
- Earlier it was done through Lamination, Encapsulation, Microfilming but now the trend is towards digital preservation.

Digital Preservation:

- Storage, maintenance and accessibility of a digital object over the long term usually as a consequences of applying one or more digital preservation strategies.
- These strategies may include technology preservation, technology emulation or data migration.

Outreach Activity:

Purpose of the outreach activity is to improve reading habits, writing, and speaking skills among the students. To develop a reading culture in the student is now a need of society. Regular and constant reading can help to improve a child's concentration abilities and also help the child learn to sit and listen for a for a long period of time. Taking into consideration the Department of Library, implement programs for the children's of nearby schools.

Conclusion:

We know that library is not only a knowledge ocean, its ultimate aim is to provide satisfactory services for all the people. So in the new era, library should improve itself constantly by adopting many new IT technologies. The college Library is required to have modern IT Collections and services along with traditional collections. Libraries are to be change up to date services and developments in the modern it era.